

Transcriptional response of *Silicibacter pomeroyi* DSS-3 to dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP)

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Summary

Dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP) is an abundant organic sulfur compound in the ocean and an important substrate for marine bacterioplankton. The Roseobacter clade of marine alphaproteobacteria, including *Silicibacter pomeroyi* strain DSS-3, are known to be involved in DMSP degradation *in situ*. The fate of DMSP has important implications for the global sulfur cycle, but the genes involved in this process and their regulation are largely unknown. *S. pomeroyi* is capable of performing two major pathways of DMSP degradation, making it an important model organism. Based on the full genome sequence of this strain we designed an oligonucleotide-based microarray for the detection of transcripts of nearly all genes. The array was used to study the transcriptional response of *S. pomeroyi* cultures to additions of DMSP compared to the non-sulfur compound acetate in a time series experiment. We identified a number of upregulated genes that could be assigned to potential roles in the metabolism of DMSP. DMSP also affected the transcription of genes for transport and metabolism of peptides, amino-acids and polyamines. DMSP concentration may thus also play a role as a chemical signal, indicating phytoplankton abundance and eliciting a regulatory response aimed at making maximum use of available nutrients.

Keywords: microarray, marine bacterium, Roseobacter, messenger RNA, DMSP, transcription, sulfur metabolism

Introduction

The conversion of organic sulfur compounds by bacterioplankton is an important process in the marine environment with implications for the global sulfur cycle and climate regulation (Andreae, 1990; Simo et al., 2002).

Dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP) is produced by marine algae as an osmoprotectant (Stefels, 2000), predator deterrent (Wolfe and Steinke, 1997), and antioxidant (Sunda et al., 2002). It also represents an important carbon and sulfur source for the marine microbial food web (Yoch, 2002).

Current evidence indicates that marine bacteria possess two major pathways for DMSP degradation. The DMSP demethylation pathway metabolizes DMSP to 3-methylmercaptopropionate (MMPA) and, in some bacteria, proceeds further to methanethiol (MeSH) and acrylate or propionate (van der Maarel et al., 1996; Gonzalez et al., 1999). Incorporation of MeSH into sulfur-containing amino acids and biomass has been demonstrated for marine isolates and natural bacterioplankton communities (Gonzalez et al., 1999; Kiene et al., 1999). The DMSP cleavage pathway metabolizes DMSP to the climate-relevant dimethylsulfide (DMS) (Kiene et al., 1999).

Cultured members of the Roseobacter clade have widespread abilities to degrade DMSP via one or both pathways (Gonzalez et al., 1999; Moran et al., 2003; Miller and Belas, 2004). Several recent studies have shown this taxon to be important in DMSP degradation *in situ* (Gonzalez et al., 1999; Kiene et al., 1999; Moran et al., 2003), along with the SAR11 and Oceanospirillales groups (Todd et al., 2007). Roseobacters are therefore valuable model organisms for understanding DMSP transformation in the ocean (Rappe et al., 1997; Gonzalez et al., 2000; Zubkov et al., 2001; Moran et al., 2003).

Silicibacter pomeroyi strain DSS-3 is a Roseobacter clade member capable of both the demethylation and cleavage pathways (Gonzalez et al., 1999; Gonzalez et al., 2003). *S. pomeroyi* grows on a variety of organic acids, amino acids and other compounds, including DMSP, as sole carbon sources (Gonzalez et al., 2003). Based on these characteristics and other adaptations to living in association with marine phytoplankton evident in the *S. pomeroyi* genome sequence (Moran et al., 2004), we anticipated that the organism would exhibit a specific transcriptional response to the presence of DMSP at concentrations typical of phycospheres, that we assume to be intermediate to cytosolic and open water concentrations. Dissolved DMSP concentrations in seawater range from 5-100 nM, but concentrations in algal blooms reach 1650 nM (Yoch, 2002), and cytosolic concentrations in phytoplankton range from 40 to > 500 mM (Yoch, 2002).

Key genes of the demethylation pathway in *S. pomeroyi* (Howard et al., 2006) and the cleavage pathway in Oceanospiralles member *Marinomonas* sp. MWYL1 (Todd et al., 2007) have recently been identified, but many other genes involved in DMSP cleavage and demethylation pathways are yet to be recognized. Further, there is little information regarding regulation between these competing pathways. Microarrays have proven to be powerful tools to study transcription in microorganisms under specific growth conditions or in response to individual compounds (Schembri et al., 2003; Deneff et al., 2004; Pappas et al., 2004; Ducey et al., 2005; Methé et al., 2005). We have developed an oligonucleotide-based whole genome microarray for gene expression studies of *S. pomeroyi* strain DSS-3 and applied it to investigate the transcriptional response to DMSP. Our first objective was to generate hypotheses regarding the pathways of DMSP degradation and their regulation. Since DMSP can be considered an indicator of the proximity of phytoplankton, we also looked for evidence

of transcriptional responses that could indicate a role for DMSP as an environmental signal. Our results have implications for understanding regulatory and metabolic mechanisms in marine Roseobacters, and contribute to an improved understanding of marine sulfur cycling.

Results and Discussion

We studied the transcriptional response of *S. pomeroyi* in batch cultures that received additions of either DMSP or acetate near the end of the logarithmic growth phase. The temporal pattern of the transcriptional response was used to identify genes whose expression was changed following the addition of DMSP. Acetate served as a non-sulfur control to account for genes regulated as a general response to changes in substrate availability or other conditions in the batch cultures. Batch cultures were preferred over chemostats in this case to obtain the sampling volumes needed at the closely spaced time points, and to allow for appropriate replication (n=3) for both acetate and DMSP treatments.

Growth and activity of *Silicibacter pomeroyi*

The DMSP and acetate additions to batch cultures of *S. pomeroyi* had no significant effect on the growth rates between 20 and 240 minutes ($\mu = 0.11 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for ACET and DMSP, and 0.10 in CTRL). Cells were in logarithmic growth in a complex medium at the time of substrate addition (Fig. 1). Growth curves leveled off in all treatments after 240 min, indicating the end of logarithmic growth. The OD increased further to a maximum OD of 1.56 measured the next day. Following a lag phase of ~40 min, the DMSP concentration in DMSP-amended cultures decreased measurably and DMS and MeSH accumulated (Fig. 2). After 160 minutes, 15% of the added DMSP remained unmetabolized, 38% was recovered as DMS or MeSH and the remaining

47% was assumed to be incorporated into bacterial biomass, metabolized to other compounds, or otherwise sorbed or lost. Based on reasonable assumptions of cell size and sulfur content, the observed increase in bacterial biomass was calculated to account for 31% of the added DMSP, indicating that most of the DMSP could have been incorporated into cell biomass. Significant levels of MeSH produced in CTRL samples are likely derived from organic sulfur compounds in the complex growth medium.

Quality control of microarray data

All analyses of gene expression were based on normalized log-ratio data (see experimental procedures), where M is a measure of the mRNA abundance in the treatment sample relative to the control ($t=0$) sample. A self-self hybridization with sample CTRL-0-A indicated excellent reproducibility of the array hybridization process. Less than 5% of probes had a value of $|M| > 0.5$, indicating that a change in the normalized log ratio of ± 0.5 can be reliably detected (Fig. 3, CTRL-0-A self). Signal intensity (sum of medians of both color channels) was high with a maximum of 3.6 % of features per array falling below the detection limit. Mismatch probes designed for four high intensity probes showed an average reduction of signal intensity to 57% of the exact match signal with one mismatch, to 21% with two and to 9% with three mismatches, indicating good specificity of the probes. The average coefficient of variance of M of replicated probes with $|M| > 1$ was 20.1%.

We performed quantitative real-time PCR (Q-PCR) on selected genes and samples to independently assess if we could reproduce the polarity of the changes observed in the microarray analysis (supplementary material Table S1). Q-PCR results for each gene were normalized to SPO2904, a gene with high signal strength and

constant $M \approx 0$, indicating it was not influenced by the experimental conditions. Q-PCR confirmed higher expression in DMSP versus ACET treatments for five significantly DMSP-upregulated genes (as defined below) and higher expression in ACET versus DMSP treatments for two ACET-upregulated genes (Fig. 4A). For one gene (SPO1922) Q-PCR data showed ACET upregulation while the microarray data was ambiguous. At low signal strength, as was the case for this probe, microarray data may not always be reliable since small variations in the color channel data can lead to large changes of M . A comparison of the DMSP/ACET ratios from Q-PCR with ratios derived from microarray data showed that the measurements were significantly correlated (amplified RNA: $r=0.60$, $p<0.05$; non-amplified RNA: $r=0.71$, $p<0.001$) (Fig. 4B).

Identifying differentially regulated genes

An evaluation of the overall transcriptional response showed an increased number of genes with changed expression ($|M|>0.5$) in 40 min (Fig. 3A) and 80 min samples of both treatments as compared to 20 and 160 min samples (Fig. 3B), which is in agreement with DMSP degradation data (Fig. 2). Both treatments affected the transcription of a broad range of genes to a similar magnitude, indicating that the experimental conditions were appropriate for a comparison of treatment-specific effects. The self-organizing maps (SOM) cluster analysis used to categorize probe response into nine clusters according to the temporal patterns (Fig. 5) revealed five major temporal patterns. SOM categorized 2047 probes as DMSP upregulated (25%; clusters A1 and A2), 1757 as ACET upregulated (22%; clusters B3 and C3), 659 as DMSP+ACET upregulated (8%; cluster A3), 1046 as DMSP+ACET downregulated (13%; clusters C1 and C2), and 2588 as mostly unaffected (32%; clusters B1 and B2) (Fig. 5). The large number of genes up- or downregulated in both treatments, or

unaffected in both (53%; 4293 probes of 8097; Fig. 5), indicated that the transcriptional response was, to some degree, a general response to changing substrate availability. There was no bias in expression for genes located on the megaplasmid versus the chromosome, with 12% of potentially upregulated genes located on the megaplasmid compared to 10.4% of all genes (Moran et al., 2004).

Probes in the DMSP or ACET upregulated SOM clusters were designated as “potentially upregulated”. We then applied a fold-change criterion to the averaged microarray data ($|M| > 1$, equivalent to a minimum fold change > 2) and a significance criterion based on Significance Analysis of Microarrays (Tusher et al., 2001). Probes that fulfilled all three criteria and the corresponding genes were defined as “significantly upregulated”. Discussion focuses on the significantly upregulated genes, with potentially upregulated genes referred to as supporting evidence in some cases.

For DMSP, 117 probes representing 108 genes fulfilled our selection criteria for significantly upregulated genes (supplementary material Table S2). The majority of these genes recorded a maximum upregulation between 2 and 4-fold relative to the control. Most significant probes were also of high signal intensity; A majority (55%) ranked among the top 20% of most intense probes. In 45% of the significantly DMSP upregulated genes either both probes were significantly upregulated (nine genes) or the second probe was at least potentially upregulated. For acetate, 43 probes representing 42 genes fulfilled the selection criteria for significantly upregulated genes (supplementary material Table S3). Only 28% of ACET upregulated genes were supported by the second probe also being significantly or potentially upregulated. The significantly upregulated genes were categorized into functional groups based on annotation information, including TIGR-FAM's, PFAM's, COG's and other information (Table 1).

Known DMSP degradation genes

Genes mediating the first steps in two competing pathways for DMSP degradation have recently been identified. While not all genes involved in DMSP degradation are expected to be transcriptionally regulated by the availability of DMSP, we examined this small set of known genes for evidence of upregulation. SPO1913 (designated *dmdA*) encodes a methyl transferase that removes a methyl group from DMSP to produce MMPA (Fig. 6) (Howard et al. 2006). While not significant, SPO1913 was potentially upregulated, along with neighboring SPO1914, which shares an operon with SPO1913 based on OFS1.2 operon prediction program with a cutoff probability of 0.8 (Westover et al., 2005) and experimental evidence from reverse-transcriptase PCR transcript analysis (H. Bürgmann, unpublished data). In addition, the demethylation reaction catalyzed by DmdA (SPO1913) was shown to be dependent on the methyl carrier tetrahydrofolate (THF) (Howard et al., 2006). The microarray data show significant upregulation of SPO3016, one of two *metF* homologs in the *S. pomeroyi* genome. In *Streptomyces lividans* and other bacteria, *metF* (EC 1.5.1.20) converts 5,10-methylene THF to 5-Methyl THF as part of a cyclical pathway that regenerates THF for methyl group transfer (Blanco et al., 1998). The second *metF* ortholog (SPO1862) was indicated as essential for MeSH production by a transposon mutant library (Table 2). These results indicate that both *metF* homologs may play a role in methyl group transfer during DMSP degradation.

SPO1703 is a homolog to acyl CoA transferases (designated *dddD*) that mediate the addition of a CoA moiety to DMSP in the first step of DMS formation (Fig. 6) in *Marinomonas* and some other bacteria (Todd et al., 2007). One probe for SPO1703 was potentially upregulated and also fulfilled the fold-change but not the significance criterion. The second probe showed no treatment effect. Although weak,

this evidence for upregulation strengthens the idea that this gene is also involved in DMSP cleavage in *S. pomeroyi*.

Putative DMSP degradation genes

Significantly upregulated SPOA0318 is annotated as a methionine gamma lyase, an enzyme shown to convert methionine to MeSH, ammonium, and 2-oxobutanoate in various bacteria (Manukhov et al., 2005). The reverse phenotype (MeSH to methionine) has been demonstrated experimentally in *S. pomeroyi* as part of the DMSP degradation pathway, and is thought to be a critical mechanism by which some marine taxa obtain reduced sulfur for amino acid synthesis (Kiene et al., 1999). Upregulation of SPOA0318 in the presence of DMSP might indicate that this homolog mediates the formation of methionine from MeSH. However, an ortholog to SPOA0318 was not found in the (draft) genome sequence of *Roseovarius nubinhibens* ISM, the other sequenced Roseobacter with experimentally demonstrated assimilation of DMSP-derived sulfur into amino acids. This may indicate the existence of alternative enzyme systems. Kiene et al. (Kiene et al., 1999) have suggested cystathionine gamma synthetase for this function, but we found only weak homologs to known cystathionine gamma synthetases in the *S. pomeroyi* and *R. nubinhibens* genomes.

A library of *S. pomeroyi* transposon mutants screened for disruption of MeSH production from DMSP (Howard et al., 2006) contained mutants with a transposon insertion in SPO3169, an ATP-dependent Clp protease A subunit gene (*clpA*) (Table 2). The experimental evidence for involvement of this gene in DMSP degradation coincides with the significant upregulation of three genes from the Clp proteolytic system (*clpA*, SPO3169; *clpP*, SPO1003; *clpX*, SPO1004) and a *dnaK* homolog (SPO0043). The Clp system and *dnaK* act as chaperones in *E. coli* and other organisms

(Wickner et al., 1994; Reid et al., 2001), suggesting that chaperone activity may be required for functionality of one or more enzymes mediating DMSP degradation.

The significantly upregulated SPO3557, together with SPO3558 and SPO3559, is predicted to encode a dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) reductase (Fig. 6), an enzyme that usually catalyzes the reduction of DMSO to DMS as a terminal electron transfer reaction during anaerobic growth in Bacteria and Archaea (McEwan et al., 2002). In the present study, *S. pomeroyi* was presumed to be growing aerobically, although the high cell density and rich medium raise the possibility of microaerophilic conditions. Indeed, it has been shown experimentally that *S. pomeroyi* can reduce added DMSO to DMS under laboratory culture conditions similar to the ones used here (Gonzalez et al., 1999). An alternative hypothesis is that the DMSO reductase is catalyzing the reverse reaction to oxidize DMS to DMSO (Fig. 6). *S. pomeroyi* has been shown to degrade DMS that has either been added directly to cultures or produced by the bacterium during degradation of DMSP (Gonzalez et al. 1999). The mechanism by which DMS is further degraded has not yet been determined.

Miscellaneous sulfur-related genes

Two sulfatases were among the significantly DMSP upregulated genes. SPO3286 is identified as an arylsulfatase, and SPO0800 as a putative choline sulfatase (EC 3.1.6.6.). Described choline- and aryl-sulfatases release sulfate from various sulfate esters, in a process found to be irreversible in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Lucas et al., 1972; 2000). Sulfatases have been found to be regulated by the sulfur status of the cell, and are upregulated in cells grown on organic sulfur sources in absence of inorganic sulfur (Hummerjohann et al., 2000). *S. pomeroyi* is exposed to high concentrations of sulfate both in the experiment and in the natural environment, but it has been shown that DMSP and other reduced sulfur compounds are preferred sulfur

sources for this bacterium (Kiene et al. 1999). Upregulated gene SPO2215 is one of many glyoxalase family proteins in the *S. pomeroyi* genome (PFAM group PF 00903); glyoxalase 1 (E.C. 4.4.1.5) is a well-characterized member of this group of proteins involved in the formation and lysis of carbon-sulfur bonds according to the BRENDA database (Schomburg et al., 2002).

Putative propionate moiety degradation genes

Pathways for the metabolism of the three-carbon propionate moiety of DMSP are not currently known. It is generally thought that acrylate is formed during DMSP degradation by either the demethylation or cleavage pathway (Fig. 6) (Yoch, 2002; Moran et al., 2003), and accumulation of acrylate was indeed observed in the *S. pomeroyi* transposon mutant of the *dmdA* gene (SPO1913) (Table 2). For DMSP cleavage, it was recently proposed that 3-hydroxy propionate is formed instead of acrylate (Todd et al., 2007). Pathways for acrylate degradation have been discussed in the literature, for example via 3-hydroxy propionate (Ansedè et al., 1999), lactate, or propionyl-CoA and succinate (Fernandez-Briera and Garrido-Pertierra, 1988). The significantly upregulated SPO0740 and SPO0370 are acyl-CoA reductase type genes with roles in fatty acid metabolism (protein families PF00378 and TIGR01751, respectively), indicating a possible involvement in the degradation of the three carbon moiety. The KEGG database lists SPO0740 as the candidate enzyme for transforming acryloyl-CoA to 3-hydroxypropionyl-CoA (Fig. 6), indicating a 3-hydroxy propionate pathway.

However, other upregulated genes would be in agreement with a pathway involving succinate as an intermediate. The significantly upregulated SPO0361 is a succinate dehydrogenase (EC 1.3.99.1), a well-known TCA cycle enzyme that converts succinate to fumarate (Hederstedt and Rutberg, 1981). Some genes for intermediate

steps, such as acyl-CoA dehydrogenase-like genes for the conversion of acryloyl-CoA to propionyl-CoA (SPO3804, SPO0693, SPO1968, SPO0879, SPOA0288), and methylmalonyl-CoA epimerase (SPO0932) for the conversion of (S)-methylmalonyl-CoA to (R)-methylmalonyl-CoA are among potentially upregulated genes. It is quite possible that *S. pomeroyi* uses more than one pathway in its metabolism of the DMSP carbon chain depending on whether demethylation or cleavage is the initial step. Given the high amounts of potentially toxic acrylate assumed to be produced from DMSP, such metabolic flexibility may be important to the organism, allowing metabolism of the three carbon moiety under aerobic and microaerophilic conditions (Tholozan et al., 1992).

DMSP transport genes

It was previously hypothesized that DMSP uptake in *S. pomeroyi* would involve a glycine betaine-type transporter system (Moran et al., 2004), a view strengthened by the identification of the betaine-carnitine-choline transporter family gene *dddT* on an operon with other genes required for DMS production in *Marinomonas* (Todd et al., 2007). Although several probes for such genes were potentially DMSP-upregulated, none of them fulfilled our significance criteria. However it is noteworthy that both probes for the *dddT* homolog SPO3186 are putatively upregulated and each fulfills one of the other significance criteria. Transposon disruption of the SPOA0068 gene, which is part of an ABC transporter for polar amino acid uptake (SPOA0068-71) resulted in a DMS- and MeSH-negative mutant (Table 2), the expected phenotype for a DMSP transport mutant. We found significant upregulation of SPOA0073, a gene that shares an operon with this transporter and contains a protein-tyrosine-phosphatase conserved domain (COG0394) implicated in cellular signaling and regulation in *Yersinia* sp. (Kolmodin and Aqvist,

2001). Based on this evidence, SPOA0068-71 and SPO3186 are both candidates for the uncharacterized DMSP transporter in *S. pomeroyi* (Fig. 6), and SPOA0073 may have a role in regulation of DMSP uptake.

Genes not directly related to DMSP degradation

The relative distribution of the upregulated genes among the role categories showed that DMSP-upregulated genes included a high percentage of transport genes and genes from intermediary metabolism, specifically sulfur and nitrogen metabolism (Table 1). DMSP upregulated genes also included higher percentages of genes involved in protein fate and amino-acid biosynthesis and metabolism, as well as genes for protein synthesis. Seven genes with regulatory function were among DMSP upregulated genes, but none were found among ACET upregulated genes. This differential representation of role categories suggest a transcriptional response specific to DMSP and involving a diversity of genes.

We were intrigued by the high number of transport-related genes affected by DMSP addition. Two amino acid transporters (SPO1831, SPOA0099), two peptide transporters (SPO0599, SPO2554), and one polyamide/spermidine/putrescine (SPO2699) transporter were among the upregulated genes. Polyamines are produced by a wide variety of eukaryotes and prokaryotes, including phytoplankton (Tabor and Tabor, 1984; Lu and Hwang, 2002), and coastal seawater concentrations can reach concentrations 30 nM in coastal seawater during algal blooms (Nishibori et al., 2003).

Further, SPO2627 and SPO2628 encode two subunits of a TRAP transporter annotated as a carbohydrate/C4-dicarboxylate uptake system, SPO1837 is a putative sugar transporter, and SPO0783 is a phosphonate transporter. In addition there are several significantly upregulated transporters with unclear substrate specificity

(SPO0027, SPO0797, SPO3402, SPO3613, SPO2187, SPO2418). Up to fourteen transporters were upregulated in response to the addition of a single compound.

In agreement with the upregulation of amino acid and oligopeptide transporters, other upregulated genes were predicted to be involved in the processing of peptides and amino acids, and in general with energy metabolism. SPO3717 is a putative cytosol aminopeptidase, SPO2603 is an amidohydrolase possibly involved in histidine energy metabolism, and SPO3374 is a purine biosynthesis protein on a predicted operon with several potentially upregulated peptidases.

It has been hypothesized that the unusually high number of peptide-, aminoacid- and polyamine-transporters in the *S. pomeroyi* genome are linked to the phytoplankton-associated lifestyle commonly observed among marine Roseobacters (Moran et al., 2004). Our results suggest that transport and processing of typical phytoplankton exudates like peptides, amino acids, and polyamines was stimulated by the presence of DMSP. While we cannot yet rule out the possibility that these upregulated genes are directly involved in DMSP metabolism, it seems unlikely. Therefore, we hypothesize that at concentrations that may occur in algal blooms or near phycospheres, DMSP or one of its metabolites acts as a signal that triggers upregulation of multiple genes for harvesting and processing compounds associated with nutrient-rich algal cells. The fact that the amino acid- polyamine and peptide-related genes were upregulated by DMSP but not by acetate suggests a specific signal rather than a general reaction to increased substrate availability. The idea of DMSP as a cellular signal is supported by the observation that the closely related marine bacterium *Silicibacter* sp. TM1040 has been shown experimentally to exhibit chemotactic behavior towards DMSP (Miller et al., 2004).

Conclusions

The temporal development of global expression profiles of *S. pomeroyi* during growth on DMSP was successfully examined by comparative microarray analysis with acetate as a non-sulfur-containing substrate. The study had two main purposes: first, to find candidates for the many unidentified genes in the DMSP degradation pathways based on the assumption that some of these genes are transcriptionally regulated by the availability of DMSP; second, to use genome-wide transcriptional data to search for evidence of co-regulation of DMSP metabolism with other cellular processes. The broad transcriptional response to the experimental conditions was evaluated by combining analysis of temporal patterns (SOM), statistical significance, and magnitude of the observed change. The microarray data were successful in generating testable hypotheses about the metabolic processing of DMSP by *S. pomeroyi*, including: a) Methionine gamma lyase (SPOA0318) catalyzes the synthesis of methionine from MeSH via the reverse reaction from its characterized function. b) Chaperone activity mediated by the Clp system is important for one or more steps in DMSP degradation. c) A homolog to a branched-chain amino acid transporter (SPOA0068) is a component protein of an ABC-type DMSP transporter. d) DMSO reductase (SPO2557-2559) plays a role in DMSP degradation. e) DMSP acts as a signal compound for the proximity of phytoplankton. Figure 6 summarizes further candidate genes involved in the different pathways of DMSP degradation that can be tested in future experiments with genetic tools (Howard et al. 2006). Although the current experiment was conducted under laboratory conditions in batch culture in a rich medium, and should thus be interpreted with caution, our observations of the transcriptional response provide an interesting view on the ecological strategy of a cultured representative of the Roseobacter clade, a successful bacterial group in ocean surface waters. *S. pomeroyi*, was found to be

capable of rapidly and broadly responding to the availability of DMSP in its environment and adapted to take maximum advantage of the presence of phytoplankton.

Experimental Procedures

Array design

The array design is based on the complete genome sequence of *S. pomeroyi* strain DSS-3 (Moran et al., 2004) (accession numbers CP000031 and CP000032). A fully annotated version of the genome is available at www.roseobase.org. Probes for all identified potential genes were designed by Combimatrix Inc. using proprietary software. Probes fulfilled the following conditions: 35 to 40 bp length, probe hybridization melting temperature (T_m) between 70 and 75°C, difference in T_m to best match crosshybridization target > 12°C, and a worst case probe hairpin T_m of <40°C. The probe length criterion was relaxed to > 30 bp for a total of 48 probes, which otherwise would have resulted in the corresponding genes not being represented on the array. A total of 4161 genes out of the 4348 identified potential genes in the *S. pomeroyi* genome are represented on the array. When possible, two probes per gene were designed. For 224 genes only a single probe fulfilled the selection criteria. Fourteen genes were duplicates of other genes so only one probe set could be designed for both versions. No probes could be designed for 86 genes with short sequences or with high sequence similarity to other genes. No probes were designed for 87 genes for tRNA, miscellaneous RNA and pseudogenes.

Due to the limited number of available spots, 1928 probes for genes of particular interest were replicated on three spots per array, and 6215 probes were not replicated. Probes to be replicated were selected based on preliminary microarray data

indicating possible up-regulation in DMSP; genes unique to, and shared with, other sequenced members of the Roseobacter clade; genes matching keyword searches related to sulfur cycling, regulation, and transport; and the most strongly transcribed genes from a list containing hypothetical genes and genes matching selected COG groups (C: Energy metabolism and conversion, G: Carbohydrate transport and metabolism. E: Amino acid transport and metabolism). For testing assay specificity, 15 probes were selected and mismatch probes containing one, two, and three mismatches were designed for each. Mismatch probes were also replicated.

The final chip design contained 8143 user-designed probes distributed over 11999 spots, plus 545 manufacturer-designed quality control probes and 149 empty spots used for background correction.

Experimental conditions and sampling

Nine flasks containing 200 ml sterile modified ½ strength YTSS medium (4 g yeast extract, 2.5 g tryptone peptone, 20 g sea salts / l) were inoculated with 200 µl of a *S. pomeroyi* strain DSS-3 starter culture (OD 0.7) in 500 ml Erlenmeyer beakers covered with aluminum foil. An additional sterile control was not inoculated. Cultures were incubated in a horizontal shaker at 30°C in the dark for 17 hours, shaking vigorously at 150 rpm. Three cultures were selected as controls (CTRL). From each, 18 ml of culture were mixed with 2 ml stop solution (95% ethanol, 5% phenol (pH 8)) in sterile 50 ml Corning centrifuge tubes on ice. The cell suspension was centrifuged for 10 min at 5000 x g at 4°C and cell pellets were frozen at -80°C (CTRL samples a-c). An additional 20 ml of culture were frozen in 50 ml Corning tubes at -20°C for chemical analysis.

Immediately, three cultures were amended with DMSP to a final concentration of 80 μM DMSP (DMSP treatments a-c) and three cultures were amended with acetate at a final concentration of 140 μM (ACET treatments a-c) as a non-sulfur organic compound for comparison with DMSP. Both additions were small relative to the carbon content in the complex medium used for growth (~ 180 mM C). Different DMSP and acetate concentrations were selected to result in comparable growth rates. DMSP was synthesized by the method of Chambers (Chambers et al., 1987).

DMSP and ACET cultures were sampled in parallel at 20, 40, 80, and 160 minutes after substrate addition. At each time point duplicate 9 ml samples were taken from each culture and added to 1 ml stop solution in a sterile 15 ml Corning tube, and processed as described for CTRL samples. Optical density was determined at 600 nm in a spectrophotometer in composite samples. To calculate bacterial production and sulfur incorporation in biomass, we used the following parameters: OD 1.00 = 6.4×10^8 cells (measured by microscopic counts), a cellular biovolume of $0.4 \mu\text{m}^3$ (based on electron micrographs in Gonzalez et al., 2003), a conversion factor of 5.6×10^{13} g C / μm^3 (Bratback, 1985) and carbon and sulfur contents in dry mass of 50% and 1%, respectively (Loferer-Kröbber et al., 1998).

For analysis of DMSP degradation products DMS and MeSH, the experiment was repeated using a different sampling scheme. After addition of DMSP at time 0, 20 ml samples of each replicate culture were transferred to four sterile serum vials (one for each time point) fitted with gas-tight Teflon-coated plugs. DMSP vials were incubated under the same conditions as the culture vessels for 20, 40, 80, and 160 minutes, CTRL vials for 0, 60, 120, and 180 minutes. Dimethyl sulfide (DMS) and methanethiol (MeSH) accumulation in the headspace was measured by using a gas chromatograph (8610-C, SRI inc., Las Vegas, NV) fitted with a 6 foot, 1/8 inch

Chromosil 330 column (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA) and flame photometric detector (FPD) according to the methods of de Souza and Yoch (de Souza and Yoch, 1995) and Steinke et al. (Steinke et al., 1998). The column temperature was 60°C; the flow rate of nitrogen carrier gas was 60 ml min⁻¹. MeSH standards were from a permeation tube (VICI metronics, Poughkeepsie, NY). DMS standards were generated from alkali hydrolysis of DMSP. DMSP standards were prepared in 10 ml YTSS medium and concentrations were determined by alkali hydrolysis with 5 ml 4M NaOH followed by measuring DMS in the headspace. Henry's Law corrections were based on the calculations of Staudinger (Staudinger and Roberts, 2001) or Steinke et al. (Steinke et al., 1998).

RNA extraction, purification and amplification

Frozen cell pellets were resuspended on ice in 3 ml Tri Reagent (Ambion, Austin, TX). A 1.5 ml aliquot of the suspension was lysed by bead-beating with 0.5 ml zirconia beads for 10 minutes on a vortex adapter (Vortex-Genie 2, MoBio laboratories, inc., Carlsbad, CA) at top speed. Beads were separated by centrifugation. Chloroform (240 µl) was mixed with 1200 µl supernatant and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature. Phases were separated by centrifugation for 5 minutes at maximum speed. Approximately 750 µl of the aqueous phase were transferred to a fresh tube and mixed with 400 µl isopropanol, incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes and precipitated by centrifugation at maximum speed at 4°C for 20 minutes. Pellets were washed with cold 70% ethanol, dried, and resuspended in 90 µl RNase free water. Residual DNA was removed using the DNA-*free* kit (Ambion). RNA was purified using the MEGAclear kit (Ambion). Ribosomal RNA was removed enzymatically using the mRNA-ONLY kit (Epicentre, Madison, WI), using phenol-chloroform extraction and precipitation with ethanol for post-reaction cleanup according to instructions.

The mRNA in 1 μ l of extract (ca. 100-500 ng) was amplified using the MessageAmp Bacteria kit (Ambion), which uses polyadenylation followed by T7 in-vitro transcription to amplify RNA. The protocol was modified to accommodate indirect labeling by substituting one quarter of the UTP in the T7 reaction with aminoallyl labeled UTP (Ambion). The amplification yielded between 65 and 359 μ g of aa-aRNA (aminoallyl-labeled antisense RNA).

Labeling and microarray hybridization

A competitive hybridization scheme was used where treatment and control samples were labeled with different dyes and hybridized to the same array. Each treatment replicate was randomly paired with one of the three control replicates. The dyes used for treatment and control were alternated with each sample to minimize potential dye bias in the dataset. AlexaFluor dyes 555 or 647 (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) were used to directly label aa-aRNA. Aliquots containing 30 μ g of aa-aRNA were reduced to dryness in a vacuum concentrator and resuspended in 9 μ l coupling buffer (sodium bicarbonate, 25 mg ml⁻¹). Dye in each single-use vial was dissolved in 11 μ l DMSO, and added to the aa-aRNA, mixed, and incubated for 1 hour in the dark at room temperature. Labeled aa-aRNA was purified using the MEGAclean kit and concentrated by reprecipitation with ethanol and resuspending in 10 μ l RNase free water. One μ l was used to determine concentration and dye incorporation (NanoDrop ND 1000, Nanodrop technologies, Wilmington, DE). The remainder was fractionated using RNA fragmentation reagents (Ambion). A 10 μ l aliquot of each labeled and fractionated aa-aRNA sample was hybridized for 16 hours at 45°C to the *S. pomeroiyi* array on the Combimatrix Custom Array platform according to the manufacturer's standard protocol for RNA hybridization.

Image acquisition and analysis

Arrays were scanned with an Axon GenePix 4000B microarray scanner (Molecular Devices Corporation, Sunnyvale, CA) at 5 μm resolution. Images were acquired and analyzed using GenePix Pro 6.0 software. Background correction was achieved by subtracting the mean of the 5 closest empty spots on the array. Bad spots were identified visually and by mean vs. median plots for each color channel, and flagged accordingly. Result files for all arrays using the AF555 dye for the treatment sample were color channel-swapped. Data processing and analysis was performed with Acuity 4.0 software. Microarray data have been deposited in NCBI's Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO, <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>) and are accessible through GEO Series accession numbers GSM125367-125378, GSM126249-126259, and GSM127048.

Microarray data analysis and quality assurance

The detection limit was defined per array as average Sum of Medians (SM) of the 149 empty spots + 2 x their standard deviation. Low intensity spots which fell below the detection limit, features flagged as bad, empty features, and quality assurance features were excluded from analysis. Changes in transcription were analyzed based on log ratio data according to:

$$M' = \log_2 \frac{\tilde{I}_{SAMP}}{\tilde{I}_{CTRL}}$$

where \tilde{I} is the background-corrected median of pixel intensities for the color channel assigned to a treatment (SAMP) or control (CTRL) sample, respectively. M' values were Lowess-normalized for each array dataset to compensate for linear or non-linear dye bias (Yang et al., 2002) and averaged for replicated spots (M). A combined

dataset was created by averaging the M values of the arrays for experimental triplicates. Self Organizing Maps (SOM) cluster analysis was performed with the Acuity software package (Molecular Devices Corporation, Sunnyvale, CA) on the combined data, using a 3 x 3 cluster matrix, Euclidean squared similarity metric, and data centering. Lists of genes fulfilling fold change criteria were created based on $|M| > 1$, indicating a two-fold change relative to the control sample. Non averaged M data for all microarrays was exported to Excel and Significance Analysis of Microarrays (SAM) was performed with the program SAM version 2.11 (Tusher et al., 2001). ACET and DMSP treatment arrays were analyzed separately as ‘one class time course’ problems using the signed area trend indicator and 100 permutations. The false discovery rate was set to $< 10\%$.

Lists of “significantly upregulated” probes for each treatment were obtained by selecting probes that clustered in the appropriate potentially-upregulated SOM clusters, showed more than two-fold change in at least one of the averaged data set points of the appropriate treatment for any time point, and were found to be significantly upregulated in the SAM analysis for that treatment. Lists of “potentially upregulated” probes for each treatment were obtained by selecting probes that clustered in appropriate SOM clusters but did not meet all of the other criteria.

Role category information was obtained from TIGR Comprehensive Microbial Resource (<http://cmr.tigr.org/tigr-scripts/CMR/CmrHomePage.cgi>). Assignment of *S. pomeroiyi* genes to potential gene functions was based on protein family designations available from the existing genome annotation (Moran et al., 2004) (<http://www.roseobase.org/>), and assignment to Clusters of Orthologous Groups (COGs) through BLASTp (Altschul et al., 1997) against the COG database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/COG/new/>). Based on this information, detailed

information on putative gene functions, including known substrates and products, involvement in pathways, reversibility, etc. was retrieved from the BRENDA (<http://www.brenda.uni-koeln.de/index.php4>) (Schomburg et al., 2002) and KEGG (<http://www.genome.jp/kegg/pathway.html>) (Kanehisa et al., 2006) databases.

Quantitative RT-PCR

Nine genes were analyzed by quantitative real-time PCR to independently check microarray results. Five genes were randomly selected from the list of DMSP significantly upregulated genes, two from the ACET significantly upregulated genes, and two were genes that did not exhibit significant variation. Primers were designed for each gene using Primer3 online primer design software (http://frodo.wi.mit.edu/cgi-bin/primer3/primer3_www.cgi). Primers are listed in Table S1. Transcripts were quantified in amplified (antisense) RNA and non amplified RNA extracts treated with the mRNA-ONLY kit. All replicates of 40 and 80 minute samples of DMSP and ACET treatments were analyzed. Amplified RNA samples were diluted 1:10 prior to reverse transcription. All RNA samples were quantified spectrophotometrically and reverse transcribed with random hexamer primers at a concentration of $0.3 \mu\text{g } \mu\text{l}^{-1}$ using the OmniScript reverse transcription kit according to manufacturers instructions. A control reaction omitting reverse transcriptase was prepared for each sample. Standards for real-time PCR were obtained from a dilution series of RNase-treated genomic *S. pomeroyi* DNA over six orders of magnitude. Duplicate real-time quantitative PCR reactions containing 1 μl of each reaction or standard, each primer at a final concentration of 10 pM, and 1 x IQ SYBR Green Supermix (BioRad, Hercules, CA). Real time PCR was performed on an iCycler IQ Multicolor Real-Time PCR Detection System (BioRad).

The temperature program consisted of an initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 min, 45 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 45 sec and annealing at 64°C for 1 min 30 sec. Identity of amplified product was confirmed through melting curve analysis. Copy numbers of each gene were first normalized to the SPO2904 gene, and ratios between averaged values for DMSP and ACET treatments are reported.

Transposon mutant library

Creation, screening and sequencing of the *S. pomeroyi* transposon mutant library is described in Howard et al. (Howard et al., 2006). Briefly, a random transposon mutant library of *S. pomeroyi* was created using EZ-Tn5 <KAN-2> Tnp Transposome Kit (Epicentre) with the addition of TypeOne Restriction Inhibitor (Epicentre). Mutants were grown overnight in artificial seawater medium and screened with Ellman's reagent (5,5-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid; 1 mM final concentration). Gas chromatographic analysis of MeSH and DMS production in mutant cultures were conducted as described above.

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References

- Altschul, S.F., Madden, T.L., Schaffer, A.A., Zhang, J., Zhang, Z., Miller, W., and Lipman, D.J. (1997) Gapped BLAST and PSI-BLAST: a new generation of protein database search programs. *Nucleic Acids Res* **25**: 3389-3402.
- Andreae, M.O. (1990) Ocean-atmosphere interactions in the global biogeochemical sulfur cycle. *Mar Chem* **30**: 1-29.
- Ansele, J.H., Pellechia, P.J., and Yoch, D.C. (1999) Metabolism of acrylate to beta - hydroxypropionate and its role in dimethylsulfoniopropionate lyase induction by a salt marsh sediment bacterium, *Alcaligenes faecalis* M3A. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **65**: 5075-5081.
- Blanco, J., Coque, J.J.R., and Martin, J.F. (1998) The folate branch of the methionine biosynthesis pathway in *Streptomyces lividans*: Disruption of the 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase gene leads to methionine auxotrophy. *J Bacteriol* **180**: 1586-1591.
- Bratbak, G. (1985) Bacterial Biovolume and Biomass Estimations. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **49**: 1488-1493.
- Chambers, S.T., Kunin, C.M., Miller, D., and Hamada, A. (1987) Dimethylthetin can substitute for glycine betaine as an osmoprotectant molecule for *Escherichia coli*. *J Bacteriol* **169**: 4845-4847.
- de Souza, M., and Yoch, D. (1995) Purification and characterization of dimethylsulfoniopropionate lyase from an alcaligenes-like dimethyl sulfide-producing marine isolate. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **61**: 21-26.
- Denef, V.J., Park, J., Tsoi, T.V., Rouillard, J.-M., Zhang, H., Wibbenmeyer, J.A. et al. (2004) Biphenyl and benzoate metabolism in a genomic context: Outlining genome-wide metabolic networks in *Burkholderia xenovorans* LB400. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **70**: 4961-4970.
- Ducey, T.F., Carson, M.B., Orvis, J., Stintzi, A.P., and Dyer, D.W. (2005) Identification of the iron-responsive genes of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* by microarray analysis in defined medium. *J Bacteriol* **187**: 4865-4874.
- Fernandez-Briera, A., and Garrido-Pertierra, A. (1988) A degradation pathway of propionate in *Salmonella typhimurium* LT-2. *Biochimie* **70**: 757-768.

- Gonzalez, J.M., Kiene, R.P., and Moran, M.A. (1999) Transformation of sulfur compounds by an abundant lineage of marine bacteria in the alpha -subclass of the class proteobacteria. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **65**: 3810-3819.
- Gonzalez, J.M., Simo, R., Massana, R., Covert, J.S., Casamayor, E.O., Pedros-Alio, C., and Moran, M.A. (2000) Bacterial community structure associated with a dimethylsulfoniopropionate-producing north atlantic algal bloom. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **66**: 4237-4246.
- Gonzalez, J.M., Covert, J.S., Whitman, W.B., Henriksen, J.R., Mayer, F., Scharf, B. et al. (2003) *Silicibacter pomeroyi* sp. nov. and *Roseovarius nubinhibens* sp. nov., dimethylsulfoniopropionate-demethylating bacteria from marine environments. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* **53**: 1261-1269.
- Hederstedt, L., and Rutberg, L. (1981) Succinate dehydrogenase - a comparative review. *Microbiol Rev* **45**: 542-555.
- Howard, E., Henriksen, J.R., Buchan, A., Reisch, C., Bürgmann, H., Welsh, R. et al. (2006) Bacterial taxa that limit sulfur flux from the ocean. *Science* **314**: 649-652.
- Hummerjohann, J., Laudenbach, S., Retey, J., Leisinger, T., and Kertesz, M.A. (2000) The sulfur-regulated arylsulfatase gene cluster of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a new member of the *cys* regulon. *J Bacteriol* **182**: 2055-2058.
- Kanehisa, M., Goto, S., Hattori, M., Aoki-Kinoshita, K.F., Itoh, M., Kawashima, S. et al. (2006) From genomics to chemical genomics: new developments in KEGG. *Nucleic Acids Res* **34**: D354-357.
- Kiene, R.P., Linn, L.J., Gonzalez, J., Moran, M.A., and Bruton, J.A. (1999) Dimethylsulfoniopropionate and methanethiol are important precursors of methionine and protein-sulfur in marine bacterioplankton. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **65**: 4549-4558.
- Kolmodin, K., and Aqvist, J. (2001) The catalytic mechanism of protein tyrosine phosphatases revisited. *FEBS Lett* **498**: 208-213.
- Loferer-Krossbacher, M., Klima, J., and Psenner, R. (1998) Determination of Bacterial Cell Dry Mass by Transmission Electron Microscopy and Densitometric Image Analysis. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **64**: 688-694.
- Lu, Y.H., and Hwang, D.-F. (2002) Polyamine profile in the paralytic shellfish poison-producing alga *Alexandrium minutum*. *J Plankton Res* **24**: 275-279.
- Lucas, J.J., Burchiel, S.W., and Segel, I.H. (1972) Choline sulfatase of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Arch Biochem Biophys* **153**: 664-672.

- Manukhov, I.V., Mamaeva, D.V., Rastorguev, S.M., Faleev, N.G., Morozova, E.A., Demidkina, T.V., and Zavilgelsky, G.B. (2005) A gene encoding L-methionine γ -lyase is present in enterobacteriaceae family genomes: Identification and characterization of *Citrobacter freundii* L-methionine γ -lyase. *J Bacteriol* **187**: 3889-3893.
- McEwan, A.G., Ridge, J.P., McDevitt, C.A., and Hugenholtz, P. (2002) The DMSO reductase family of microbial molybdenum enzymes; Molecular properties and role in the dissimilatory reduction of toxic elements. *Geomicrobiol J* **19**: 3-21.
- Methé, B.A., Webster, J., Nevin, K., Butler, J., and Lovley, D.R. (2005) DNA microarray analysis of nitrogen fixation and Fe(III) reduction in *Geobacter sulfurreducens*. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **71**: 2530-2538.
- Miller, T.R., and Belas, R. (2004) Dimethylsulfoniopropionate metabolism by Pfiesteria-associated *Roseobacter* spp. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **70**: 3383-3391.
- Miller, T.R., Hnilicka, K., Dziedzic, A., Desplats, P., and Belas, R. (2004) Chemotaxis of *Silicibacter* sp. strain TM1040 toward dinoflagellate products. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **70**: 4692-4701.
- Moran, M.A., Gonzalez, J.M., and Kiene, R.P. (2003) Linking a bacterial taxon to sulfur cycling in the sea: studies of the marine roseobacter group. *Geomicrobiol J* **20**: 375-388.
- Moran, M.A., Buchan, A., Gonzalez, J.M., Heidelberg, J.F., Whitman, W.B., Kiene, R.P. et al. (2004) Genome sequence of *Silicibacter pomeroyi* reveals adaptations to the marine environment. *Nature* **432**: 910-913.
- Nishibori, N., Matuyama, Y., Uchida, T., Moriyama, T., Ogita, Y., Oda, M., and Hirota, H. (2003) Spatial and temporal variations in free polyamine distributions in Uranouchi Inlet, Japan. *Marine Chemistry* **82**: 307-314.
- Pappas, C.T., Sram, J., Moskvina, O.V., Ivanov, P.S., MacKenzie, R.C., Choudhary, M. et al. (2004) Construction and validation of the *Rhodobacter sphaeroides* 2.4.1 DNA microarray: Transcriptome flexibility at diverse growth modes. *J Bacteriol* **186**: 4748-4758.
- Rappe, M.S., Kemp, P.F., and Giovannoni, S.J. (1997) Phylogenetic diversity of marine coastal picoplankton 16S rRNA genes cloned from the continental shelf off Cape Hatteras, North Carolina. *Limnol Oceanogr* **42**: 811-826.
- Reid, B.G., Fenton, W.A., Horwich, A.L., and Weber-Ban, E.U. (2001) ClpA mediates directional translocation of substrate proteins into the ClpP protease. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **98**: 3768-3772.
- Schembri, M.A., Kjaergaard, K., and Klemm, P. (2003) Global gene expression in *Escherichia coli* biofilms. *Mol Microbiol* **48**: 253-267.

- Schomburg, I., Chang, A., and Schomburg, D. (2002) BRENDA, enzyme data and metabolic information. *Nucleic Acids Res* **30**: 47-49.
- Simo, R., Archer, S.D., Pedros-Alio, C., Gilpin, L., and Stelfox-Widdicombe, C.E. (2002) Coupled dynamics of dimethylsulfoniopropionate and dimethylsulfide cycling and the microbial food web in surface waters of the north atlantic. *Limnol Oceanogr* **47**: 53-61.
- Staudinger, J., and Roberts, P.V. (2001) A critical compilation of Henry's law constant temperature dependence relations for organic compounds in dilute aqueous solutions. *Chemosphere* **44**: 561-576.
- Stefels, J. (2000) Physiological aspects of the production and conversion of DMSP in marine algae and higher plants. *J Sea Res* **43**: 183-197.
- Steinke, M., Wolfe, G.V., and Kirst, G.O. (1998) Partial characterisation of dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP) lyase isozymes in 6 strains of *Emiliania huxleyi*. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* **175**: 215-225.
- Sunda, W., Kieber, D.J., Kiene, R.P., and Huntsman, S. (2002) An antioxidant function for DMSP and DMS in marine algae. *Nature* **418**: 317-320.
- Tabor, C.W., and Tabor, H. (1984) Polyamines. *Ann Rev Biochem* **53**: 749-790.
- Tholozan, J.L., Touzel, J.P., Samain, E., Grivet, J.P., Prensier, G., and Albagnac, G. (1992) *Clostridium neopropionicum* sp. nov., a strict anaerobic bacterium fermenting ethanol to propionate through acrylate pathway. *Arch Microbiol* **157**: 249-257.
- Todd, J.D., Rogers, R., Li, Y.G., Wexler, M., Bond, P.L., Sun, L. et al. (2007) Structural and regulatory genes required to make the gas dimethyl sulfide in bacteria. *Science* **315**: 666-669.
- Tusher, V., Tibshirani, R., and Chu, C. (2001) Significance analysis of microarrays applied to ionizing radiation response. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* **98**: 5116-5121.
- van der Maarel, M.J.E.C., van Bergeijk, S., van Werkhoven, A.F., Lavernman, A.M., Meijer, W.G., Stam, W.T., and Hansen, T.A. (1996) Cleavage of dimethylsulfoniopropionate and reduction of acrylate by *Desulfovibrio acrylicys* sp. nov. *Arch Microbiol* **166**: 109-155.
- Westover, B.P., Buhler, J.D., Sonnenburg, J.L., and Gordon, J.I. (2005) Operon prediction without a training set. *Bioinformatics* **21**: 880-888.
- Wickner, S., Gottesman, S., Skowyra, D., Hoskins, J., McKenney, K., and Maurizi, M.R. (1994) A molecular chaperone, ClpA, functions like DnaK and DnaJ. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* **91**: 12218-12222.

- Wolfe, G.V., and Steinke, M. (1997) Grazing-activated chemical defence in a unicellular marine alga. *Nature* **387**: 894.
- Yang, Y.H., Dudoit, S., Luu, P., Lin, D.M., Peng, V., Ngai, J., and Speed, T.P. (2002) Normalization for cDNA microarray data: a robust composite method addressing single and multiple slide systematic variation. *Nucl Acids Res* **30**: e15.
- Yoch, D.C. (2002) Dimethylsulfoniopropionate: Its sources, role in the marine food web, and biological degradation to dimethylsulfide. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **68**: 5804-5815.
- Zubkov, M.V., Fuchs, B.M., Archer, S.D., Kiene, R.P., Amann, R., and Burkill, P.H. (2001) Linking the composition of bacterioplankton to rapid turnover of dissolved dimethylsulphoniopropionate in an algal bloom in the North Sea. *Environ Microbiol* **3**: 304-311.

Figure Legends

Figure 1: Average optical density at 600 nm wavelength (OD_{600}) of *S. pomeroyi* DSS-3 cultures, following addition of DMSP or acetate to cultures grown aerobically at 30°C for 17 hours at $t=0$. Each data point represents a single measurement of a composite sample from three replicate cultures for each treatment.

Figure 2: A) DMSP, DMS and MeSH concentrations in *S. pomeroyi* cultures with DMSP addition at $t=0$ and in controls (CTRL) receiving no substrate addition. Error bars show the standard deviation of three experimental replicates. DMSP concentrations in CTRL and ACET samples were below detection.

Figure 3: Histograms of lowess-normalized log ratio data (M) averaged from triplicate microarray experiments. Shown are four different time point / treatment combinations that illustrate the change in transcription at different time points. A self-self hybridization of control sample CTRL-0-A is included for comparison in both panels. Large ($M>1$) or small ($M<-1$) values indicate genes with a twofold or greater change of expression as compared to the CTRL sample, $M=0$ indicates equal expression levels in both samples. A) Microarray analysis of 40 minute samples shows DMSP and ACET having a similar overall effect on the distribution of lowess-normalized log ratio data. Comparison with the self-self control hybridization indicates that transcription has changed for a large number of genes. B) Early and late samplings (20 and 160 minutes) showed comparatively small changes versus the control and are more similar to the self-self control hybridization data than the 40 minute samples in panel A.

Figure 4: Validation of microarray data by quantitative real-time PCR. A) Expression of selected genes in DMSP treatment relative to the corresponding ACET treatment based on Q-PCR measurements. QPCR data for each gene was normalized to a control gene (SPO2904). SPO2627, SPO3083, SPOA0318, SPO2215, and SPO3557 are significantly upregulated during growth on DMSP according to microarray analysis. SPO3322 and SPO1443 are significantly upregulated during growth on ACET. SPO1922 appeared unchanged in microarray analysis. Filled bars are 80 minute samples, open bars are 40 minute samples. B) correlation of DMSP / ACET ratios of gene expression based on q-PCR measurements and microarray data. The q-PCR results are based on unamplified mRNA extracts (open squares, dashed line) or amplified aRNA (×, solid line).

Figure 5: Self-organizing maps (SOM) analysis of averaged Lowess-normalized log ratio data (M). Green denotes probes downregulated relative to the control, red indicates upregulated. Lines show average behavior for each cluster. DMSP and ACET time courses were concatenated for this analysis and data was centered (normalized to the mean). Labels along the top of the maps indicate treatment (DMSP or acetate), time point (20, 40, 80 or 160 min) and that data was averaged for the three experimental replicates (A, B, C). SOM patterns A1 and A2 represent genes with indicate increased expression following addition of DMSP but not ACET.

Figure 6: Hypothesized pathways of DMSP degradation in *S. pomeroyi* DSS-3. Solid rectangles indicate genes that were significantly upregulated in the presence of DMSP in the microarray study or share an operon with a significantly upregulated gene. Dashed rectangles indicate potentially upregulated genes. Asterisk indicates that transposon disruption of this gene affected MeSH and / or DMS production.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Table 1. Comparison of distribution of significantly upregulated probes and genes among functional role categories for DMSP and ACET treatments. The number in parentheses indicates additional probes with possible membership in the role category but for which annotations are putative. The number of genes differs from the number of probes because one or both probes for a given gene may be upregulated.

Functional Group	DMSP		ACET	
	Number of probes	Percent of genes ^a	Number of probes	Percent of genes ^a
Transport and binding proteins	19 (3)	19	2 (0)	5
Central intermediary metabolism general	1	1	0	0
<i>Sulfur metabolism</i>	4	4	0	0
<i>Nitrogen metabolism</i>	3	3	0	0
Energy metabolism general	13 (0)	11	3 (1)	9
<i>Fatty acid metabolism</i>	6 (1)	6	2 (0)	5
<i>Energy storage / Energy metabolism</i>	2	1	0	0
Amino acid biosynthesis / metabolism	5 (1)	6	1 (0)	2
Biosynthesis of cofactors	1	1	2	5
Translation and protein synthesis, modification	14 (1)	12	1 (-)	2
Protein fate	3	3	0	0
Cell processes	2	2	0	0
DNA replication, repair , modification, transposon	2	2	3	7
Transcription	1	1	1	2
Cell structure	2(0)	2	0 (1)	2
Regulatory function	6 (1)	6	0	0
Toxin production and resistance, detoxification	2	2	1	2
Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown	24	20	25	58
All probes	117		43	

^a Percentage of significantly upregulated genes in this functional group among all significantly upregulated genes.

Table 2. Dimethylsulfide (DMS) and methanethiol (MeSH) gas formation by *S. pomeroyi* random transposon insertion mutants negative for thiol formation from DMSP in a colorimetric screen with Ellmann's reagent; the other phenotypes were determined by gas chromatographic analysis of mutant culture supplied with DMSP or MMPA (Howard et al. 2006).

Insertion locus	Number of independent mutants	Annotation of disrupted gene	Thiols from DMSP	MeSH from DMSP	DMS from DMSP	MeSH from MMPA	Other
SPO1913	1	<i>dmdA</i> ; Aminomethyl-transferase family protein	–	–	+	+	acrylate accumulation
SPO3169	1	<i>clpA</i> ; ATP-dependent Clp protease, ATP-binding subunit	–	–	+*	+	
SPO3804	2	Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase family protein	–	+*	+*	–	
SPOA0068	1	Polar amino acid uptake family ABC transporter, ATP-binding protein	–	–	–	–	
SPO1862	4	<i>metF</i>	–	–	– ^a	+	

* $1/3$ to $1/2$ of wild type levels.

^a One of four independent mutants showed low levels of DMS production.

Supplementary Material

Table S1. Primers used for quantitative real-time PCR analysis of gene expression.

Locus	Forward primer	Reverse primer	Product size [bp]
SPO3577	TTGGCCTGCTGTTCTTTCTT	GACCAAGGTGAAAGGTCGAG	126
SPO2215	GATCGAACTGGCGAGCTATC	TGGATGCGGTCGATATTGTA	117
SPOA0318	GGTCGTGGTCGACAATACCT	AGATATTTGGTGGCCGAATG	93
SPO3083	AGAGCTTGAAGACGGCATGT	GATTGCAGGGTGATGTCCTT	93
SPO2627	CTGGTACGAGACCAACGACA	CGGCAGTTTCTCGTATTCGT	91
SPO1922	TTCGAACAATTGCGTTTTGA	TTGATCCGATCCGAATTCCTC	80
SPO2904	TAAGCTTTCGGTCTCTGATG	ACCGTCGATTTCAGCAACTT	79
SPO1443	GCCGAGAATTTGACACCTA	ATCCTGCTCCTTGAAGCTGA	84
SPO3322	ATGATCGAGCGGTCAAGAC	CTGATATCGCCGGTCTGTTT	95

Table S2. Functional genes significantly upregulated in DMSP and their assumed functional role category. Dark grey indicates both probes from the same gene were significant. Light gray indicates the second probe was in the potentially upregulated group, borders indicate genes predicted to share an operon.

Locus	Annotation	Function
SPO0027	ABC transporter transmembrane ATP-binding protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO0043	dnaK; chaperone protein DnaK;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0222	ald; alanine dehydrogenase;	Amino acid biosynthesis / metabolism
SPO0235	aldehyde dehydrogenase family protein;	Energy metabolism
SPO0292	efflux transporter RND family MFP subunit;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO0295	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO0361	sdhB; succinate dehydrogenase iron-sulfur protein;	Energy metabolism
SPO0370	ccrA; crotonyl-CoA reductase;	Fatty acid metabolism
SPO0437	cold shock family protein;	Cell processes
SPO0450	membrane protein putative;	Putative transport and binding proteins
SPO0485	rpsS; ribosomal protein S19;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0488	rplP; ribosomal protein L16;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0500	rplF; ribosomal protein L6;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0503	rpmD; ribosomal protein L30;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0506	secY; preprotein translocase SecY subunit;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0507	adk-1; adenylate kinase;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0559	oligopeptide ABC transporter permease protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO0641	conserved hypothetical protein	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO0701	gap-1; glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase type I	Energy metabolism
SPO0740	paaB; enoyl-CoA hydratase/isomerase PaaB;	Fatty acid metabolism
SPO0783	phnE; phosphonate ABC transporter	Transport and Binding proteins

	permease protein	
SPO0797	bile acid transporter family protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO0800	choline sulfatase putative;	Sulfur metabolism
SPO0855	xylB; xylulokinase;	Energy metabolism
SPO0889	membrane protein putative;	Putative transport and binding proteins
SPO0976	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1003	clpP; ATP-dependent Clp protease proteolytic subunit ClpP;	Protein fate
SPO1004	clpX; ATP-dependent Clp protease ATP-binding subunit ClpX	Protein fate
SPO1015	3-hydroxybutyrate dehydrogenase putative;	Putative Fatty acid metabolism
SPO1024	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1057	transcriptional regulator AraC family;	Regulatory function
SPO1293	phaP; phasin PhaP;	Energy Storage / Energy Metabolism
SPO1358	glyS; glycyl-tRNA synthetase beta subunit;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO1397	hydrophobe/amphiphile efflux-1 family protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO1420	transcriptional regulator CarD family;	Regulatory function
SPO1437	linC-1; 2 5-dichloro-2 5-cyclohexadiene-1 4-diol dehydrogenase;	Energy metabolism
SPO1451	aromatic 1 2-dioxygenase alpha subunit;	Energy metabolism
SPO1652	transposase truncation;	DNA replication, repair , modification, Transposon
SPO1669	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1711	ureD; urease accessory protein UreD	Nitrogen metabolism
SPO1774	3-hydroxyanthranilate 3 4-dioxygenase;	Energy metabolism
SPO1831	livF-1; branched-chain amino acid ABC transporter ATP-binding protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO1837	sugar ABC transporter permease protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO1841	BadF/BadG/BcrA/BcrD ATPase family protein;	Fatty acid metabolism
SPO1855	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1930	lpxD; UDP-3-O-3-hydroxymyristoyl glucosamine N-acyltransferase;	Cell structure
SPO1960	beta-lactamase;	Toxin production and resistance, detoxification
SPO1975	tsf; translation elongation factor Ts;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO2023	sufB; FeS assembly protein SufB;	Biosynthesis of cofactors
SPO2074	mfd; transcription-repair coupling factor	Transcription
SPO2131	cysS; cysteinyl-tRNA synthetase;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO2157	gltA; citrate synthase I;	Energy metabolism
SPO2158	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2187	TRAP transporter solute receptor TAXI family;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO2210	BNR/Asp-box repeat domain protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2215	glyoxalase family protein;	Sulfur metabolism
SPO2274	acpP; acyl carrier protein;	Fatty Acid metabolism
SPO2285	DNA-binding protein putative;	Putative Regulatory function
SPO2354	membrane protein;	Putative transport and binding proteins
SPO2412	aldolase putative;	Amino acid biosynthesis / metabolism
SPO2418	transporter LysE family	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO2439	transcriptional regulator GntR family;	Regulatory function
SPO2536	transcriptional regulator LuxR family;	Regulatory function
SPO2544	amidohydrolase family protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2554	peptide/opine/nickel uptake family ABC transporter periplasmic substrate-binding protein;	Transport and Binding proteins

SPO2603	N-formylglutamate amidohydrolase family protein;	Amino acid biosynthesis / metabolism
SPO2617	SPFH domain/band 7 family protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2627	TRAP transporter DctQ subunit;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO2628	TRAP transporter solute receptor DctP family;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO2642	YeeE/YedE family protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2699	opine/polyamine ABC transporter permease protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO2707	bacterial luciferase family protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2726	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2750	trimethylamine methyltransferase family protein;	Energy metabolism
SPO2795	aminotransferase DegT/DnrJ/EryC1/StrS family;	Putative amino acid metabolism
SPO2938	amidase family protein;	Putative Translation and Protein synthesis
SPO2969	gatA; glutamyl-tRNA(Gln) amidotransferase A subunit;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO3016	metF; 5 10-methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase;	Amino acid biosynthesis / metabolism
SPO3054	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3064	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3083	dxnH; 3-oxoadipate CoA-succinyl transferase beta subunit;	Fatty acid metabolism
SPO3085	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3169	clpA; ATP-dependent Clp protease ATP-binding subunit ClpA;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO3203	guanosine-3' 5'-bis(Diphosphate) 3'-pyrophosphohydrolase putative;	Cell processes
SPO3234	ATP synthase F0 B' subunit;	Energy metabolism
SPO3235	atpE; ATP synthase F0 C subunit;	Energy metabolism
SPO3286	atsA; arylsulfatase;	Sulfur metabolism
SPO3311	ADA regulatory protein putative;	Regulatory function
SPO3359	tdh; L-threonine 3-dehydrogenase;	Energy metabolism
SPO3374	purH; bifunctional purine biosynthesis protein PurH;	DNA replication, repair , modification, Transposon
SPO3402	transporter LysE family;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO3557	dimethyl sulfoxide reductase C subunit putative;	Sulfur metabolism
SPO3588	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3613	transporter LysE family;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO3715	carbonic anhydrase putative;	Central intermediary metabolism
SPO3717	cytosol aminopeptidase family protein;	Protein fate
SPO3725	penicillin-binding protein 1A family;	Cell structure
SPO3769	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3875	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPOA0073	arsC-2;arsenate reductase;	Toxin production and resistance, detoxification
SPOA0099	branched-chain amino acid ABC transporter ATP-binding protein;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPOA0106	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPOA0213	nitric oxide reductase E protein putative;	Nitrogen metabolism
SPOA0214	norD; nitric oxide reductase D protein;	Nitrogen metabolism
SPOA0318	megL; methionine gamma-lyase;	Amino acid biosynthesis / metabolism
SPOA0339	HAD-superfamily hydrolase subfamily IB;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPOA0343	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPOA0452	transcriptional regulator MarR family;	Regulatory function

Table S3. Functional genes specifically upregulated in acetate. Dark grey indicates both probes from the same gene were significant. Light gray indicates the second probe was in the potentially upregulated group, borders indicate genes predicted to share an operon.

Locus	Annotation	Function
SPO0400	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO0506	secY; preprotein translocase, SecY subunit;	Translation and Protein synthesis, modification
SPO0738	TRAP dicarboxylate transporter, DctP subunit;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO0829	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1116	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1221	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1234	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1235	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1286	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1428	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1443	rhlE; ATP-dependent RNA helicase RhlE;	Transcription
SPO1448	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1643	selenium-binding protein putative	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1721	TRAP dicarboxylate transporter, DctP subunit, putative;	Transport and Binding proteins
SPO1741	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1905	fumC; fumarate hydratase class II	Energy metabolism
SPO1926	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO1927	site-specific recombinase, phage integrase family;	DNA replication, repair , modification, Transposon
SPO2047	pgl; 6-phosphogluconolactonase;	Energy metabolism
SPO2109	guaA; GMP synthase;	DNA replication, repair , modification, Transposon
SPO2243	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2508	conserved domain protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2649	conserved domain protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO2855	cobalt chelatase, pCobT subunit;	Biosynthesis of cofactors
SPO3088	OmpA family protein;	Putative Cell structure
SPO3167	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3322	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3359	tdh; L-threonine 3-dehydrogenase;	Amino acid biosynthesis / metabolism
SPO3375	conserved hypothetical protein	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3590	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3600	pyk; pyruvate kinase;	Energy metabolism
SPO3602	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3637	uvrC; UvrABC system protein C;	DNA replication, repair , modification, Transposon
SPO3638	oxidoreductase, short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family;	Putative energy metabolism
SPO3733	phhB; 4a-hydroxytetrahydrobiopterin dehydratase	Biosynthesis of cofactors
SPO3832	ornithine cyclodeaminase/mu-crystallin family protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPO3855	gpsA; glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (NAD(P)+);	Fatty acids and phospholipid metabolism unclassified, unknown
SPO3899	conserved hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPOA0203	hypothetical protein	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown
SPOA0402	polyketide synthesis domain protein;	Toxin production and resistance, detoxification

SPOA0403	acyl-CoA dehydrogenase family protein;	Fatty acid metabolism
SPOA0410	hypothetical protein;	Hypothetical, unclassified, unknown